

DEVELOPMENT OF ANALYTICAL SKILLS IN PHYSICS LESSONS IN KAZAKHSTAN SCHOOLS THROUGH THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE**Kachnova O.***Master of 1-st course,
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named after Sh. Yessenov, s. Aktau, Kazakhstan***Abstract**

This article investigates the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in cultivating analytical and critical thinking skills among schoolchildren in Kazakhstan's physics classes. By incorporating AI-driven simulations, personalized tasks, and automated data analysis, the study explores how AI can enhance the learning process, making complex scientific concepts more interactive and accessible. The main focus is on equipping students with essential skills such as verifying information reliability, developing hypotheses, identifying and correcting errors, and applying a critical approach to data analysis.

Unlike traditional teaching methods, AI offers students the opportunity to experiment with physics concepts in a virtual environment, receiving immediate feedback that enhances understanding and engagement. This interactive approach encourages students to deepen their grasp of physical phenomena, making learning more active and exploratory.

The article also examines the readiness of educators to adopt AI tools, considering Kazakhstan's specific educational and cultural context. Successful implementation of AI requires teachers who are well-prepared and supported, along with careful alignment to the country's educational values. Cultural adaptation is essential, as Kazakhstan's educational approach is rooted in traditional methods, and the transition to digital tools must respect these foundations.

Moreover, this study emphasizes that AI should not replace traditional teaching but rather act as a complementary resource. Hands-on experiments, teacher-led discussions, and direct interaction remain invaluable in physics education. AI's role is to support and enrich traditional methods, providing students with enhanced tools to strengthen critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical abilities that will serve them well in future scientific studies and real-world applications.

In conclusion, AI has the potential to significantly enhance physics education in Kazakhstan by fostering critical and analytical skills among students. However, realizing these benefits fully requires a thoughtful approach to integration that respects cultural norms, ensures teacher readiness, and maintains a balance with traditional methods to maximize educational outcomes.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, critical thinking, analytical skills, physics in schools, educational technologies, interactive simulations, personalized learning, Kazakhstan.

Introduction

Physics requires students not only to possess strong knowledge but also to develop a deep understanding, the ability to analyze data, and critically evaluate information. To succeed in physics, a student must connect theory with practice, comprehend physical phenomena and laws, and cultivate analytical thinking skills. In today's world, artificial intelligence (AI) can play a pivotal role in fostering these skills, transforming the learning approach.

AI makes physics education more interactive, visual, and accessible. It enables students to experiment, analyze, and problem-solve while receiving immediate feedback. This technological approach has the potential to unlock students' abilities, spark greater interest in the subject, and significantly enhance educational outcomes. This article will explore how AI contributes to developing analytical skills in physics lessons, as well as the challenges that may arise during its implementation.

Physics is one of the disciplines in which analytical skills play a key role. To solve problems, conduct

experiments, and analyze results, students must be able to work with data, formulate hypotheses, and test them. In this context, AI offers unique opportunities for in-depth subject study.

AI systems provide students access to interactive simulations that model physical processes that would be challenging or costly to reproduce in reality. For instance, these simulations allow students to adjust parameters and observe how results change. This helps them understand the relationship between theoretical concepts and practical outcomes.

Imagine students studying the law of motion for an object on an inclined plane. Using AI, they can change the angle of inclination, initial velocity, and other parameters to observe how these affect the object's speed and distance traveled. This promotes analytical thinking by allowing students to independently observe results, analyze them, and draw conclusions rather than just memorizing formulas.

AI can adapt to each student's knowledge level, offering personalized assignments and tests. This allows students to work at their own pace, progressively

deepening their understanding and skills. Adaptive testing, which adjusts task difficulty based on the student's proficiency, helps identify areas of strength and weakness, motivating further development.

AI-based systems can also analyze data and present results in an accessible format for students. For example, during experiments, AI can generate an immediate graphical representation of data, helping students interpret results more quickly. This allows them to focus on data interpretation rather than complex mathematics, which is especially beneficial for students who struggle with calculations.

In addition to analytical abilities, it is essential that students develop critical thinking skills—a key objective of modern education, especially in technical subjects like physics. Critical thinking involves analyzing information, evaluating its reliability, asking questions, and forming and testing hypotheses. In this context, artificial intelligence (AI) can serve as a powerful tool for fostering these skills when used thoughtfully and with a clear educational purpose.

AI enables students to engage with physics not only through passive learning but also through active interaction with information, cultivating skills in data analysis and critical evaluation. The following sections will discuss how AI supports the development of critical thinking in schoolchildren as they study physics.

1. The Skill of Data Verification and Critical Evaluation of Information

Using AI in physics provides students with a unique opportunity to work with models that generate results based on specific algorithms. This requires them to assess the validity of the data they receive. For example, when studying the motion of an object on an inclined plane, AI might offer a model under ideal conditions—no friction, constant acceleration, etc. However, such idealized conditions rarely exist in real life, and it is the teacher's role to highlight the importance of critically evaluating these models.

This raises the question: "How accurate are the results provided by AI?" Students are taught to ask clarifying questions, such as:

- What hypotheses or assumptions did the AI use?
- Under what conditions would this model provide accurate results, and when would it not?
- How can I adjust the model parameters to better reflect reality?

These questions form the foundation of critical thinking, allowing students not only to accept the results but also to understand how and why they were obtained. In this way, AI becomes a valuable tool that encourages students to critically analyze and validate data.

2. Formulating Hypotheses and Testing Them Independently

AI empowers students to create and test hypotheses, a critical component in developing critical thinking. Rather than memorizing experiment results, students learn to formulate assumptions and put them to the test. For instance, a student might hypothesize that increasing the angle of inclination will raise the speed of a body rolling down the plane. With AI, they can test

this hypothesis by adjusting the angle in the simulation and observing the outcome.

This is more than a technical exercise; it's real practice in critical thinking. Students gain the opportunity to ask questions, explore ideas, and analyze results. AI enables them to quickly and safely repeat experiments multiple times, varying conditions to see how changes impact the outcome. The ability to revisit a hypothesis, modify it, and test it builds perseverance in the search for a vital truth trait for a critically minded individual.

3. Development of Analytical and Error-Handling Skills

When working with AI, students learn to consider errors and analyze inaccuracies. Many AI-driven simulations allow them to adjust parameters and observe how even slight changes in initial data can impact results. This is essential in physics, where experiments are rarely perfect and always involve some degree of error.

AI systems can include modules for automated error analysis, helping students recognize the importance of evaluating data for reliability and accuracy. For example, when simulating free fall under Earth and Moon conditions, AI can illustrate differences, such as acceleration due to varying gravitational forces, and provide tools for measuring and analyzing discrepancies. This teaches students to not only work with outcomes but also understand how errors and changes in conditions affect final results.

4. Ability to Ask Questions and Seek Alternative Explanations

Critical thinking is incomplete without the capacity to ask questions, explore alternative explanations, and consider different perspectives. Through AI, students can "push the boundaries" of tasks and consider other factors that might influence results. For instance, when conducting a virtual experiment on friction, they might ask how the outcome would change if the surface had a different texture or if the object's weight varied.

AI enables students to pose these questions and find answers through simulations that mimic a variety of conditions. This practice helps students see physics as more than just a set of rules; it's a science that invites interpretation and explanations based on changing conditions. AI becomes a safe testing ground, where every mistake becomes a learning step towards understanding.

5. Analysis of Conclusions and Feedback

A crucial aspect of critical thinking is the ability to analyze and evaluate conclusions while correcting errors. AI-based systems can provide students with feedback on their approach, highlighting successful steps and identifying mistakes. For example, if a student misinterprets data, AI can offer hints or explanations, guiding them back to the point of error and helping them refine their approach.

This method cultivates an analytical mindset toward drawing conclusions. AI can also present alternative solutions, demonstrating that multiple approaches can lead to the same result. This way, students gain experience not only in correcting mistakes but also in recognizing that solutions in physics can be multifaceted.

6. Developing a Habit of Systematic Information Verification

Using AI in physics lessons encourages students to cultivate a valuable habit: systematically verifying information. Working with AI models and simulations teaches students to pay close attention to details and consistently question the accuracy and validity of results. This skill can be applied not only in physics but across other subjects and in daily life, fostering the ability to critically assess information.

This approach lays the groundwork for independent thinking, where students move beyond merely consuming information to actively filtering, comparing, and rechecking it. In an age where digital information is readily accessible, critical verification of data and the skill to distinguish reliable sources from unreliable ones are invaluable competencies that AI can help develop.

Thus, when used effectively, AI can be a powerful tool for fostering critical thinking among students. It aids in mastering theoretical content while also teaching analysis, data verification, and hypothesis formulation skills. The key to this is a thoughtful pedagogical strategy, in which AI serves as a partner, helping students develop their own analytical and thinking abilities.

For AI to truly benefit students, teachers must consciously structure the learning process so that students not only receive answers but also learn to question the given results, seek alternative explanations, and consider data from multiple perspectives. As a result, AI transforms from merely a technology into an active component of the educational process, encouraging students to independently seek the truth and expand their ability to critically engage with information.

Despite the vast potential of AI in education, its integration into the educational process presents several serious challenges.

Firstly, substantial training is required for teachers, especially those from older generations who are accustomed to traditional methods and may find it challenging to master new technologies. Many experienced teachers rely on conventional teaching approaches, and a sudden shift to AI may be difficult for them. Special training is necessary to provide these educators with the knowledge and confidence to use digital tools effectively, an essential step without which AI cannot become truly beneficial in education.

Secondly, with extensive use of AI, there is a risk that students may start to rely too heavily on technology, diminishing their ability to analyze tasks independently. This can foster a dependence on gadgets and lower levels of critical thinking. Therefore, it is crucial to blend AI use with traditional teaching methods to maintain a balance between independent thinking and digital support.

Additionally, the implementation of AI requires technical infrastructure, including modern equipment and reliable internet access—factors that may pose challenges, as not all schools in Kazakhstan have equal access to these resources. In major cities, schools may have modern computers and stable internet, enabling the use of AI in classrooms. However, in rural areas,

this is often not the case, limiting the adoption of such technologies and creating disparities in educational opportunities.

The cultural characteristics of Kazakh society also significantly influence AI adoption in education. In Kazakhstan, teachers are traditionally viewed not only as sources of knowledge but also as respected mentors, with a role that extends beyond merely conveying information. It is therefore important that AI is seen not as a replacement for the teacher but as a tool that enhances the teacher's role. AI should be integrated in a way that supports and complements traditional methods, rather than replacing them.

Kazakh educators can use AI to demonstrate experiments that are difficult to reproduce in real life or to deepen the understanding of topics being studied. This way, students will view AI as an assistant that makes complex concepts more accessible while preserving the teacher's role as a personal mentor. This approach helps maintain cultural values and creates a balanced learning experience.

For AI to effectively develop students' analytical skills, several key recommendations should be followed. First, it is essential to prepare teachers by organizing training courses to build their confidence in using AI and teaching students how to work with it. Combining AI with traditional methods is also important—digital tools should not replace classical approaches to analysis and critical thinking. For instance, conducting both virtual and real experiments allows students to compare and analyze results.

Additionally, teachers should focus on fostering critical thinking skills, helping students learn how to verify information, make hypotheses, and analyze data. Teachers can encourage students to ask questions and critically evaluate AI-generated results, thereby strengthening their independent thinking skills.

Lastly, ensuring equal access to technology is crucial. This will require infrastructure improvements in rural schools so that all students can benefit from AI, including investments in modern equipment and reliable internet access.

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence is not just a tool but a transformative force in physics education, offering students new ways to engage with and understand complex concepts. By integrating AI-driven simulations, data analysis tools, and personalized learning experiences, educators can make physics more accessible and inspiring for a broader range of learners. AI enables students to visualize abstract theories, conduct virtual experiments, and receive immediate, actionable feedback, which deepens their understanding and analytical skills in a way traditional methods often cannot.

However, the success of AI in education depends on how thoughtfully it is implemented. While technology brings numerous benefits, it also raises important questions about accessibility, the role of human interaction in learning, and data privacy. Not all schools may have the resources to implement AI uniformly, risking an educational divide. Furthermore, while AI can simulate and predict, it should complement rather than replace traditional hands-on experiments and

teacher-student interactions that are critical to a well-rounded understanding of physics.

Ultimately, when carefully integrated, AI has the potential to be a powerful catalyst for students to not only learn physics but to think like physicists—to hypothesize, experiment, analyze, and apply knowledge creatively. By equipping students with these essential skills, AI can help nurture a generation that is better prepared to tackle the scientific and technological challenges of tomorrow.

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